

Generative Adversarial Networks, Zero Sum Games, Narcissistic Abuse, Multi-Person Coping Mechanisms, Angels and Demons, Hasatan the Heavenly Prosecutor

Robert Hewson - Who is Nothing Without God and Those Around Him

Generative Adversarial Networks

A Generative Adversarial Network is a strategy that consists of two neural networks, a generator network which creates data and a discriminator network (Google Developer GAN Course). Both the discriminator and the generator start out clueless and the generator learns to generate believable fake data through being judged by the discriminator. The discriminator is penalized and learns when it either misclassifies real data as fake, or fake data as real. Eventually if the generator succeeds perfectly, then the discriminator will have a perfect 50% accuracy and it will not be able to distinguish real data from fake data. Essentially the generator “fakes it till it makes it” and the generator “keeps it real”. This generative adversarial network pattern is also referenced as a “Zero Sum Game” or a situation where “one network’s gain is another’s loss”. This is because the both the gain of the discriminator and generator are dependent on the other losing.

Credit Google

1

Generative adversarial networks are unsupervised learning algorithms. This means that we do not need to have labelings or understandings of our data for us to gain information from our experiences. The information is instead gained through the

adversarial process between the discriminator and the generator.

Narcissistic Personality Disorder

Individuals with Narcissistic Personality Disorder often overestimate their capabilities or hold themselves to unreasonably high standards (Cleveland Clinic). They also tend to brag or over-exaggerate about their achievements. They have frequent fantasies about having or deserving things like success and power, and they believe in superiority. However they feel a need for admiration from others to help support their confidence in this “false self”. People with Narcissistic Personality Disorder also tend to view the world in zero-sum terms.

Generative Adversarial Cope

Narcissistic abuse is a poorly defined term that often involves the individual with “Narcissistic Personality Disorder” gaslighting an individual for the reason of receiving validation that their false self is passable and trying to hide the falseness of this self by any means necessary. They tend to be extremely unapologetic in this manner. This is almost identical to the generator wanting to fool the discriminator. This relationship between the individual with NPD and the “victim” is often a form of co-dependency, where generators and discriminators in GAN’s are definitionally co-dependent. It is also completely reasonable that the end goal would be something that is significantly superior to whatever is currently going on, because the discriminator then would move towards a solution that is to a significantly higher standard than what is currently present because they are gaining information by arguing with the generator (Individual with NPD). We want things to get better instead of worse for obvious reasons so the “Generator” individual is grandiose in their actions. This would also make sense because the development of Narcissistic Personality Disorder is generally triggered by trauma and poor life conditions, something of which an unknown solution is needed as if they knew the solution the life conditions would not be poor. (Cleveland Clinic). To be on the other side of the “abuse” causes feelings of being unsure of oneself, significant trust issues, and often involves some form of attachment as well. These are both qualities of the discriminator. This re-definition is necessary for understanding, the removal of stigma, and accelerated solutions.

Angels and Demons - Hasatan the Heavenly Prosecutor

It is said in the Bible that “demons” will possess people and they will try to mislead you from God and attempt to deceive you. It is also said that demons cannot repent and are doomed for judgement. These demons fight in spiritual warfare against angels and god’s people. If you view each action from these individuals in a vacuum it is easy to get angry for the deception, however there is no need to apologize as the “angelic” individuals being prosecuted are simultaneously being led towards god over time. In the Old Testament the role of the devil is more in line with this framework, as more of an angelic “heavenly prosecutor” role. By trying to mislead you from God, the devil is more of a “training ground”. This version of the devil challenges you towards better things as well as a better relationship with God, was never technically evil, and does not need to apologize for what it is doing. It is also mentioned somewhere in the bible that evil in the end never wins. The most important thing is the separation of the “demon” and the individual who is “possessed”. This allowed these people to not have to bear moral responsibility for things done while coping, such as dishonesty. These narcissistic traits are also commonly found in highly important areas where we are in desperate need of solutions, such as medicine.

Medical Gaslighting - Two Birds One Stone Approach

Sometimes it is completely unreasonable that with all of the poor choices an individual makes in a day that a doctor would be able to find out what is wrong with them, particularly as the medical industry moves towards shorter and shorter appointment times where you have less of a personal relationship with your doctor. Sometimes this pain might be too much for a practitioner to bear, and they might enter into a state of denial or self-deceival. However what if this state of self-deceival also turned into them playing the role of the deceiver, sticking their head in the sand while holding your hand? An extremely common complaint of medical doctors is things being written off as “just anxiety” unapologetically. This tends to infuriate people, and they begin to argue with the doctor about why it is not “just” anxiety. It is within this framework that quite a lot of people become argumentative, *as they should*.

Bibliography

Turning your attention to narcissistic personality disorder. Cleveland Clinic. (2025, September 16). <https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/diseases/9742-narcissistic-personality-disorder>

Google Developer GAN Course. Google. <https://developers.google.com/machine-learning/gan> 5